

Comprehension of Government Accounting Systems to Improve Liability of Financial Institution

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Abstract: The public demand for public transparency causes government accounting to be important. The greater the funds managed by the government the greater the demand for financial accountability as a form of financial transparency in government. The purpose of community service is firstly to understand the understanding of UNJ's financial department employees for the government accounting system, secondly to ensure the socialization of regulatory changes in the financial accountability of the institution is well understood by the finance staff, the third is to find solutions to the limited human resources that understand Accounting system of the financial section in the process of preparing financial statements. Participants attend this training as many as 26 people, namely the representatives of the Central Finance Staff and Faculty of the State University of Jakarta, the results of the implementation of an understanding of the new government regulations on the preparation of financial statements and increasing the skills of participants in government financial accountability.

Keywords: Comprehension of Government, Government Accounting System, Institutional Accountability

I. Introduction

A paradigm shift in the field of governance in the post reform era become a major topic in the new paradigm of governance in Indonesia (Nasution, 2018). Apparatus The government has an element of community service need first to appreciate and apply them according to the demands of the change. Whereas the old paradigm that has been the aspect pemerintahan with a tendency to power and now turned into the authority for public service, community empowerment (Nasution, 2019).

In line with the changes in the reform era, both internally and strategic environmental changes which is a necessity every civil servants (officials) understand and melaksanakannya well. Since the beginning of reform in 1998, has brought about many changes in the life of the nation that has profound implications in governance and development in Indonesia (Nasution, 2019). Through democratization and decentralized zation, openness, transparency, accountant profitability, the implementation in state in the region as a hallmark of good governance or good governance such (Nasution, 2019).

In the era of globalization and increasing demands for reform, the role of accounting as a means of recording increasingly needed. The sake of it is not only devotes to the management of an entity, but also to the needs on accountability (accountability) the many people in need, In the world of business (Commercial), accounting has berkembang in line with the development of the business (Nasution, 2019). This causes the accounting should be menyesuaikan and develop along with the development of the business world (Nasution, 2019).

Accounting developments pemerintahan not as fast as the business accounting (Nasution, 2019). The cause is unchanged. With the demands of society led to government accounting is important. The more the amount of funds managed by the government, the greater the demands on financial accountability as a form of financial transparency in government. Based on the above, it can be identified various issues as follows:

1. Is the finance department had to get an understanding of the accounting system The government has?
2. Are socialization regulatory changes in the financial accountability institutions are well understood by the finance department?
3. What are the limitations tbbsp who understand the accounting system of the finance department can count resistor in the process of preparation of financial statements that good?

Based on the identification of the problems above, the formulation of the problem in this rakat masya- service program is socialization entails understanding Accounting System To Improve Financial Accountability Agencies (Nasution, 2018).

Participants who will attend this training is planned as 30-40 persons, namely representatives of Central Finance Department staff and faculties of the State University of Jakarta. The training aims to:

1. Improving the ability of staff to be able to understand the financial part of the accounting system The government has.
2. Improving the ability of staff to be able to understand the financial part of the regulatory changes in the financial accountability instnansi.
3. Improving the ability of expenditure of funds PPMK lola to be able to register and pela- financial Poran on the funds it manages.
4. Improving the ability of staff to be able to finance part Me- agency constructing the financial statements in accordance with applicable government regulations.

The benefits on the training to:

Trainees:

1. Participants understand the information that is accurate and timely information on the budget and financial activities of the central government.
2. Participants understand money trustworthy information about the financial position of an institution and the central government as a whole.
3. Participants understand the financial recording and reporting are useful for planning, management and control of the government's financial activities efficiently.

Community Service Team:

1. Expenditure of knowledge contributes to the community in order to empower the community and nation memcerdaskan accordance with the expenditure of the dimili- ki years of experience by the instructor.
2. Understanding the practical aspects in the preparation of financial statements efficiently.
3. Assist the Government in order to socialize the regulations so that more financial staff who understand the government accounting system.

II. Literature Review

Law No. 17 of 2003 on State Finance of Article 8 states that "in the framework of the implementation of the power over fiscal management, the Minister of Finance has the task, among others, to prepare financial statements that are accountable state budget."

Law No. 17 Year 2003 on State Finance of Article 9 states that "the Minister / Head of Institution as the budget user / users of goods Ministry / His agency has the task, among others, prepare and submit financial early lapor- State Ministry / Agency he leads."

Law No. 17 of 2003 on State Finance of Article 30 paragraph (2) states that the President submitted a draft law on state budget execution accountability to Parliament in the form of financial statements that include Budget Realization Statement, Balance Sheet, Cash Flow Statement, and Notes financial statements, which is attached with the financial statements of state enterprises and other entities (Nasution, 2019).

Act No. 1 of 2004 on State Treasury of Article 7, paragraph (20) states that the Minister of Finance as General Treasurer of the State authority establishes financial accounting and reporting system of the State (Nasution, 2019). Act No. 1 of 2004 on State Treasury of Article 51 paragraph (1) states that the Minister of Finance / Regional Financial Management Officer as General Treasurer of the State / Region held a top accounting financial transactions, assets, debt, and equity funds, including financing transactions and calculations (Nasution, 2019).

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Act No. 1 of 2004 on State Treasury of Article 51 paragraph (2) states that "the Minister / Head of institution / local work unit head as users held a joint budget accounting on financial transactions, assets, debt, and equity funds, including transactions revenue and expenditure which are within his responsibility."

Act No. 1 of 2004 on State Treasury of Article 55 (1) states that "the Minister of Finance as fiscal managers preparing for the Central Government Financial Statements submitted to the President in order to meet pertanggungjawab- an implementation of the state budget"

Act No. 1 of 2004 on State Treasury of Article 55 (2) states that "in preparing the Financial Statements of the Central Government where the as- referred to in paragraph (1), the minister / head of institution as Budget User / User Ba- rang prepare and submit financial statements that include the Budget Realization report, Balance Sheet and Notes to the financial statements including financial reports from the General Services Agency on the state ministries / Institutions respectively."

The explanation of the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 1 Year 2004 concerning State Treasury, states that "in order that the information presented in the financial statements of government can SETS nuhi principles of transparency and accountability, should be organized Central Government Accounting System (SAPP) which consists of the Central Accounting System (SIAP) which ments sanakan by the Ministry of Finance and Agency Accounting System (SAI) carried out by the state ministries / agencies."

Law No. 36 of 2004 on the Budget of Fiscal Year 2005. Article 17 paragraph (1) states that "after ending the 2005 fiscal year, the Government prepares Accountability for Implementation of the State Budget for Fiscal Year 2005 in the Financial Statements."

Presidential Decree No. 42 Year 2002 on Guidelines for the Implementation of the State Budget in Article 60 paragraph (1) states that "the Minister / Head of accountability shall run movement menyeleng- proper use of the funds they control part of the budget in the form of reports on realization of the budget and balance of State Ministries / Agencies concerned kepa- da President through the Minister of Finance. The Presidential Decree has been amended by Presidential Decree No. 72 of 2004 on Guidelines for the Implementation of the State Budget."

Central Government Accounting System (SAAP) applies to all organizational units of the Central Government and the Local Government accounting unit in implementation of Deconcentration and / or Duty The reader assistance and the implementation of the Financial Budget and Estimates. According to the Law on state finances, which are not included in the coup ling- SAPP is:

1. Local Government (the funds originate from the budget);
2. State-Owned Enterprises / Regional-Owned Enterprises which consists of;
3. Limited Liability Company, and;
4. General Company;
5. The government and the Bank-Owned Financial Institution.

Aim from SAPP menurut Noordiawan (2009) are:

1. Keeping assets (safe guarding assets), so that government assets can be maintained through a series of processes recording, processing and consistent financial Poran pela- accordance with the standards.
2. Provide relevant information, providing accurate information and timely about the budget and financial activities of the central government.
3. Provide reliable information about the financial position of an institution and the central government as a whole.
4. Provide financial information that is useful for planning, managing, and controlling government activities and finances efficiently.

Based on the PMK No. 171 / PMK.05 / 2007 on Accounting and Financial Reporting System of the Central Government, SAPP has two (2) subsystems, namely the State General Treasurer Accounting System (SA-BUN) and Institution Accounting System (SAI).

SA-BUN, implemented by the Ministry of Finance as nutrient Repository of the State General / Chief Financial Officer (CFO). Furthermore, SA-BUN has several subsystems, namely:

1. Central Accounting System (SIAP);
2. System Accounting debt Government and Grants (SAUP & H);
3. Transfer to the Regional Accounting System (SA-TD);
4. Forward Accounting System Pin- era (SA-PP);
5. The government has Investment Accounting System (SA-IP);
6. Sus Khu- Transaction Accounting System (SA-TK);
7. Accounting Systems BE- lanja Subsidies and Other (SA-BSBL);
8. Other Agency Accounting System (SA-BL).

SAI has two (2) subsystems, namely the Financial Accounting System (SAK) and on Management Information Systems and State Goods (SIMAK-BMN). SAI dilaksanakan by the Minister / Chairman of the Technical Institute as Chief Operational Officer (COO).

SA-BUN is a series of manual procedures as well as the most computerized ranging from early pengumpul- data recording, to reporting financial position and financial operations of the Ministry of Finance as Ben- Dahara state general. Financial Statement that produced a Budget Realization Report including financing, Balance Sheet, Cash Flow Statement, and is equipped with Notes to Financial Statements. Institution Accounting System (SAI) carried out by the ministry nega- ra / institution. The state ministries / agencies perform data processing to produce financial statements such as Budget Realization Statement, Balance Sheet and Notes to Financial Statements (Nasution, 2019).

SAK used to process transactions planned and realized, resulting in the Budget Realization Report. Medium- right-BMN SIMAK transak- the acquisition process, changes and deletion of BMN to support IFRSs in order to produce the Balance Sheet. In addition, SIMAK-BMN generate various reports, books, and cards give managerial information in the management BMN. The fundamental characteristics of the accounting system of the central government, among others:

1. Basis of Accounting
Cash toward Accrual. Accounting basis used in the financial statements of the government is cash basis for the recognition of revenue, expenditure and financing in the Budget Realization Report and on an accrual basis for the recognition of assets, liabilities, and equity in the balance sheet. Cash basis accounting is the basis which recognizes the effects of transactions and other events when cash or cash equivalent is received or paid. Accrual basis of accounting is accounting basis that recognizes the effects of transactions and other events at the time of the transaction or the event occurred, without memperhatikan when cash or cash equivalents received or paid.
2. Couples Bookkeeping System.
System Bookkeeping pairwise based on the basic accounting equation is: $Assets = Liabilities + Equity Fund$. Each transaction dibu- kukan with debit a estimates and forecasts related credits.
3. Single Fund
Accounting activities referring to the constitution, the state budget as an operational basis. This single fund Merupakan where dipertang- Government Revenues and Expenditures accounted for as a single entity.
4. Decentralization Implementation Accountant Militancy
Financial accounting and reporting activities in the agency implemented in stages by accounting units both at headquarters and in regional institutions.
5. Estimates Chart Standard
SAPP using stan- dar estimates set by the Minister Financial applicable for the purposes of budgeting and accounting.

SAPP refers to the Government Accounting Standards (SAP) in performing the recognition, assessment, recording, presentation, and the refugees when on financial transactions in the context of the preparation of the financial statements (Nasution, 2019). SAPP is divided into two subsystems, namely:

1. Central Accounting System (SIAP) is part SAPP implemented by the Directorate of Information and Accounting (DIA) which will produce a report for the central government financial accountability of the state budget. Ready itself is divided into two subsystems, namely the State Treasury Accounting System (SAKUN) and the General Accounting System (SAU).
2. Agencies accounting system (SAI) is a part of SAPP that will produce financial statements for pertanggungja- Waban implementation agency budgets. SAI itself is divided into two subsystems, namely financial accounting system (SAK) and the State Property Accounting System (SABMN).

Ready is a series of manual procedures and terkomputerisasi, ranging from data collection, recording, until the financial reporting and operations positions in the finance minister as the State Treasurer (BUN). KUN ready to process the transaction data and general accounting. Ready made up of:

1. SAKUN, ie ready subsystems that generate cash flow statement and balance sheet KUN.
2. SAU, which subsystem will SiAP produce LRA Central government.

SAI is a series of manual procedures computerized ranging from data collection, recording, up to reporting financial position and the financial operations of ministries / agencies. SAI consists of two subsystems, namely:

1. SAK; subsystem of the SAI which yield information on the LRA, balance sheet and notes to the financial statements belonging to kementerian / agencies.
2. SABMN; subsystem of the SAI which is a set of procedures that are interconnected to process originals in order to produce information to prepare balance sheets and statements of State Property and other managerial reports according to applicable regulations.

SAK as well as SAU, produce LRA, Balance Sheet, and Notes to the financial statements, but the resulting financial statements are the financial statements at the level of ministries / agencies. The organizational structure of the ministry / Institution is tiered starting from ministries / agencies to the office / work unit, because it is in the implementation, financial accounting unit established at the level. The accounting process starting from the lowest unit, the accounting unit at the office level (Nasution, 2019). The resulting financial statements will then be given to the above accounting unit to be merged. And so on, so that it will eventually obtained the financial statements at the level of ministries / agencies. Financial accounting units described in the previous section are:

1. Users Anggaran Accounting Unit (UAPA), which is at the level of Ministries / Institutions
2. Accounting Unit Vice-Echelon Peng to Articles 1 (UAPPA-E1), which is at the level echelon 1.
3. Peng Assistant Accounting Unit for Budget-Region (UAPPA-W) which is at the regional level.
4. Accounting Unit of the Budget Authority (UAKPA) situated at the level of Budget Authority (Office).

SAK as well as SAU, produce LRA, Balance Sheet, and System Accounting Goods property Country. In general, goods are part of the richness that is specific units that can be assessed / calculated / measured / weighed, not including cash and securities. According to Law No. 1 of 2004, the State Property are all goods purchased or obtained at the expense of the state budget or come from other legitimate acquisition. Examples of other legitimate acquisition is a grant or booty / encumbrances. Excluded from the definition of State are goods owned or controlled by:

1. LGs (sourced from the budget);
2. BUMN;
3. Government banks and financial institutions owned by the government.

In the central government accounting, SABMN as a subsystem of Accounting Information Systems aims to produce a balance sheet and the property area. To achieve the goal tersebut, Ministry / Agency member-tuk Goods Accounting Unit as follows:

1. User Accounting Unit of Goods (UAPB), at the level of the Ministry / Institution. Penanggungjawabnya is the minister / head of institution.
2. Accounting Unit Vice-Echelon Peng to Item 1 (UAPPB-E1), which is at the level echelon 1.
3. Assistant Accounting Unit Peng-to Goods-Region (UAPPB-W) which is at the regional level.
4. Accounting Unit Authorized Goods (UAKPB) situated at the level of budget for User Authority (office).

Goods Accounting Unit, in addition to the process of the source document to produce a report of state property, are also required to coordinate with the Financial Accounting Unit for the preparation of Neraca and in preparing the notes specifically note of the state property. In the operation pemerintahan, the government is using the principle of:

1. Decentralization; nanggungjawab submission by the government The government has to autonomous regions to organize and manage the affairs of government in the system of the Republic of Indonesia.
2. Deconcentration; nanggungjawab delegation government by Government to Governor as representatives of governments and / or to the institution of vertikal in a particular area.
3. Co-administration; assignment of the Government to the area and / or village from the provincial to the district / city and / or village as well as from the regency / city to the village to carry out specific tasks.

Funds related to the decentralization of the funds from the state budget and in its implementation is transferred directly to the Regional Treasury. This fund of funds in the form of consideration (general allocation fund, a special allocation of funds, and revenue sharing). Against this funding, reporting and accountability to do in each area (Nasution, 2016).

But for the fund of funds dekonsentrasi and assistant task, a working unit which receives reports and mempertanggungjawabkan use of these funds K / L technically related. An accountability dekonsentrasi and this co-administration will be merged with the financial statements and property of the State (which has been described SAI) to become the financial statements of the Ministry / Agency and report property of the state ministries / agencies (Nasution, 2019).

Financial Reports are output resulting from an accounting system. for government center, the resulting financial statements are the consolidated financial statements of the financial statements of two subsystems, namely: the resulting financial statements prepared and SAI. Central Government Financial Report presented to Parliament as a liability on the State Budget. Before being submitted to the Parliament, the central government's financial statements audited in advance by BPK. Government Financial Statements based on PP 71/2010 consists of:

1. Consolidated Budget Realization Report Report Realization budgets from all Kementerian / State ministries / Institutions that have been reconciled. This report equating information, shopping, transfer, surplus / deficit and financing, rest more / less financing early fencing that each compare with budgets in one period.
2. More Budget Balance report. The contents of this report, in the form of mutations Budget Balance (SAL) which accumulated balances SiLPA / SiKPA of the LRA, while the SAL reporting structure is as follows:
 - a. More Budget Balance beginning;
 - b. More Budget Balance usage;
 - c. Surplus / Less Financing Budget of the current year;
 - d. Bookkeeping Error Correction Previous year; and
 - e. Etc.
3. Government Balance
The balance of consolidated central government balance sheet feed meru- SAI and Balance SAKUN (Accounting System of the State Treasury). The report presents information in wishful keu- position of the central government with regard to assets, debt and equity fund on the date / year a certain budget.
4. Operational reports
This report as the report that specify income surplus or deficit from operations. The structure of the report is as follows:
 - a. LO income from operations;
 - b. Expenses from operations;
 - c. Surplus / Deficit from Non-Operational activities, when there is;
 - d. Extraordinary items, if any;
 - e. Surplus / deficit-LO.
5. Cash flow statement
Central Government Cash Flow Statement Cash Flow Statement is a consolidation of all the Regional Office of Directorate General of PBN. This report presents information about cash inflows and outflows for a certain period classified by operating, investing non-financial assets, financing and non-budget.
6. Notes to the Financial Statements Represents explanation or breakdown or analysis of the value of an item that is presented in Budget Realization Report, Balance Sheet and Statement of Cash Flows government in order disclosure is adequate.

III. Methodology

Framework or stages in the training Socialization Understanding Government Accounting System To Improve Financial Accountability Agencies are as follows: Based on discussions conducted by a team of community service on this training program, the finance department require this training program with the following considerations:

1. Lack of understanding of the finance department accountant system of government militancy.
2. Lack of understanding of the finance department to change the rules in the financial accountability agencies.
3. Lack of understanding of the finance department to the agency assembles the financial statements in accordance with Accounting Standards The government has.

In determining the instructional design is to be considered the following aspects:

1. The contents of the training program materials that are relevant to their needs. The team has mapped the entire material needs for the finance department which is divided into two training materials that will be described in the training material.
2. Background keu- part wishful staff such as education, main occupation, age and seba- gainya.
3. Module practices used in this training should help the participants to understand the technical aspects of the accounting system of government in the preparation of financial statements.

In order to develop a training program socialization entails understanding the accounting system of government, community service team working to develop this training both in terms of training materials, modules and question and answer in the form of relevant aspects tasian Pendokumen- and Government Financial Statements efficiently.

1. Implementation

Implementation of the training program is planned on Thursday in June 2013 in a classroom in Building N. The time allocated in the training aspect of the proposed 3 that is 4 hours of training or roughly begins at 8:30 a.m. to 14:00 pm.

2. Evaluation

The team will prepare an evaluation of community service related to the participants' understanding of training materials, implementation of the overall training to accommodate the possibility of the need for training with other materials and orderly implementation of the training program.

3. Target audience

Participants who attended as many as 30 -40 is representative of the financial department staff from both the Jakarta State University and the center of each faculty. Every part finance expected to be represented by 2-3.

The training methods used in this training program is expected to provide convenience to participants. In this training, the method used is the method of explanation, Practices and FAQ. In the method of explanation, each instructor submit related materials during 30 minutes followed by a practice session and FAQ for 30 minutes. The instructor is scheduled to make a power point slides and concise practical training modules that will be distributed to participants before the program starts.

Training aids such as LCD projectors are also used for participants to more easily understand while the other instructor training material also helped the participants to monitor the questions during the practice sessions and question and answer. Training materials will be delivered and instructors in the training program are described in the table below.

Table 1
Material Training and Instructor

Materials	Instructor	Number of hours
Concept Basic Government accounting	BPKP	1 hour
System Accounting Government	BPKP	1 hour
Stages Making Report Finance Government	BPKP	1 hour
Comprehension Report Finance (Studies Case)	BPKP	1 hour
Total Allocation Time		4 hours

IV. Results

Training activities aim to provide information about understanding the militancy accountant information system in order to further enhance the end of the financial accountability of institutions to be more effective and efficient to finance staff at the central and faculty. Through this EXERCISE pela- the participants were not only given the materials that are relevant to an understanding of accounting information systems, but also get the guidance and direction in a tough character The division formation in order to finance an increase pertanggungjawab- generated reports finance to dipertang- accounted for.

It is hoped that the participants after attending this training will have the skills and understanding in accounting information systems in an effort to improve the financial Waban pertanggungja- accordance with the agencies both in faculty or universally sitas. Understanding of Accounting Information Systems for financial staff can be used to improve kiner- ja in financial reporting agencies. The basic concept of training to build awareness in the understanding of agency accounting information system to make it more helpful and useful good. This activity has proceeded satisfactorily attended by approximately 26 participants comprising representatives of financial staff in Units, Faculties and Centers.

The training for the community can not be achieved if it can not support from the community. There is a tendency looked upon merely as a rhetorical extension it is necessary for its implementation strategy. Methods used are by approaching to the participants as a man who directly related to the issue. So that the material can be well understood would have been the method of delivery that is appropriate for it to be used method of learning simulation and debriefing. This method will stimulate participants to be interested and actively participate in these training activities.

The knowledge about the PE mahaman accounting information systems for government agencies must be known in order to finance the university and the business faculty in the management level will memjalankan BLU BLU Financial Applications which SAK- Financial Accounting System (SAK) is a subsystem of Institution Accounting System which is a series procedures that are interconnected to process the source document in order to produce information for the preparation of balance sheets and financial statements as well as other managerial reports in accordance with the provisions.

Central Government Accounting System (SAAP) applies to all organizational units of the Central Government and the Local Government accounting unit in implementation of Deconcentration and / or Duty The reader assistance and the implementation of the Financial Budget and Estimates. The purpose of the SAPP is:

1. Keeping assets (safe guarding assets), so that government assets can be maintained through a series of processes recording, processing and consistent financial Poran pela- accordance with the standards.
2. Provide relevant information, providing accurate information and timely ten- keu- pliers wishful budgets and activities of the central government.
3. Provide reliable information about the financial position of an institution and the central government as a whole.
4. Provide financial information that is useful for the planning, management, and control of govern- ment activities and finances efficiently.

Audiences and target of this activity is representative of the financial staff in the faculty of units in Universities and financial centers in the Jakarta State University. This activity is associated with institutions such as the State University of Jakarta in the finance of community service performed by lecturers seba- gai an obligation on Tridharma College.

V. Conclusion

In the era of globalization and increasing demands for reform, the role of accounting as a means of recording increasingly needed. The interest shall be intended not only for the management of an entity, but also to the needs of accountability (accountability) to the many people who memer- Lukan, In the world of business (Commercial), accounting has berkem- bang in line with the development of the business. This causes the accounting should be menyesuaikan and develop along with the development of the business world. Accounting developments not as fast as the business accounting. The cause is karak- teristiknya unchanged. With the demands of society led to government accounting is important. SEMA-kin amount of funds managed by the government, the greater the financial accountability demands form of financial transparency in the government so that the holding of training informally viding understanding of accounting systems in order to improve the financial accountability of agencies, especially at the State University of Jakarta. The results achieved in this training, participants are satisfied and pleased with the activity. Evident of attendance data, participants closely followed the activities to completion for a fixed amount and not reduced. Participants also seemed enthusiastic in giving feedback and per- tanya-an to the speaker that guide these activities. It can be concluded that this activity is very interested in the community, and some even proposed to be carried out follow-up activities.

Providing material in this training should certainly not be monotonous and bulk and uniform. It is advisable where possible to do activities that are a continuation of this activity so that the expected results more striking to the point, because this training will not obtain a satisfactory result if it is not followed up. Besides these activities had to be

developed as a form of community service in order to improve quality entails understanding the financial staff in the Jakarta State University. To conducting effective with optimal results in real benefits for the people's welfare improvement is inseparable from the support of adequate funding, so that activities can be done in a longer period of time. Expected future dianggakan the amount of funding for Community Service activities can be increased in number.

References

- [1.] Government Regulation No.24 of 2005 concerning the Government Accounting Standards Act 1 of 2004 on State Treasury Law 17 of 2003 State Finance.
- [2.] Minister of Finance Regulation No. 171/PMK.05/2007, the Ministry of Religious Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia, 2008.
- [3.] Module, the Central Government Accounting System, the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Indonesia Government Financial Accountability Acceleration Program. Director General Regulation Number of Transportation 51/Pb/2008 on Guidelines for Preparation of Financial Statements Ministries/Institutions.
- [4.] Modules, Financial System, the Ministry of Finance Republic's Indonesia Program Government Financial Accountability.
- [5.] Nasution, D. A. D. (2018). Analisis pengaruh pengelolaan keuangan daerah, akuntabilitas dan transparansi terhadap kinerja keuangan pemerintah. *Jurnal Studi Akuntansi & Keuangan*, 2(3), 149-162.
- [6.] Nasution, D. A. D. (2019). *Akuntansi Sektor Publik:(Mahir dalam Perencanaan dan Penganggaran Keuangan Daerah)*. Uwais Inspirasi Indonesia.
- [7.] Nasution, D. A. D. Reflection Critical Ethnography: Other Options Accounting Research Techniques.
- [8.] Nasution, D. A. D. (2019, August). The Effect of Implementation Islamic Values and Employee Work Discipline on The Performance of Moslem Religious Employees at Regional Financial Management in the North Sumatera Provincial Government. In *International Halal Conference & Exhibition 2019 (IHCE)* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 1-7).
- [9.] Nst, D. A. D. (2019). Pelatihan Implementasi SAP Berbasis AkruaL Pada SDM Pemerintah Provinsi Sumatera Utara (Dinas Lingkungan Hidup Provinsi Sumatera Utara). *Loyalitas, Jurnal Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat*, 2(1), 41-50.
- [10.] Nasution, D. A. D. (2019). Pengaruh Remunerasi Dan Semangat Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Pada Kantor Kejaksaan Negeri Medan. *Jurnal Akuntansi dan Bisnis: Jurnal Program studi Akuntansi*, 5(1), 71-80.
- [11.] Nasution, D. A. D. (2019). Pengaruh Implementasi Standar Akuntansi Pemerintahan Berbasis AkruaL Dan Pengawasan Kualitas Laporan Keuangan Terhadap Akuntabilitas Kinerja Instansi Pemerintah Pada Dinas Lingkungan Hidup, Dinas Kehutanan, Dan Dinas Kebudayaan Dan Pariwisata Pemerintah. *Jurnal Akuntansi Bisnis dan Publik*, 9(2), 30-43.
- [12.] Nasution, D. A. D. (2018). Analisis Pengaruh Sdm, Insentif Dan Sarana Pendukung Terhadap Implementasi Sap Berbasis AkruaL Pada Pemerintah Provinsi Sumatera Utara. *Jurnal Akuntansi Bisnis dan Publik*, 9(1), 207-218.
- [13.] Nasution, D. A. D. (2019). Faktor-Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Kinerja Pengguna Sistem Informasi Manajemen Daerah-Keuangan Pemerintah Provinsi Sumatera Utara. *Jurnal Akuntansi Bisnis dan Publik*, 10(1), 101-114.
- [14.] Nasution, D. A. D. (2019). Kebijakan Atas Kewajiban E-Filling Dalam Penyampaian Spt Tahunan Bagi Asn/Tni/Polri Dapat Diterapkan Di Seluruh Wilayah Indonesia. *Jurnal Perpajakan*, 1(2), 95-113.
- [15.] Nasution, D. A. D., Dwilita, H., & Arnita, V. (2019). Pengembangan Kewirausahaan Di SMA Negeri 1 Sunggal Kabupaten Deli Serdang Melalui Kegiatan Pelatihan Akuntansi. *Jurnal Inovasi Hasil Pengabdian Masyarakat (JIPEMAS)*, 2(2), 110-119.
- [16.] Nasution, D. A. D., & Sari, T. A. (2016). Analisis Faktor-faktor yang Mempengaruhi Implementasi SAP Berbasis AkruaL dengan Komitmen SKPD sebagai Variabel Moderating pada Pemerintah Provinsi Sumatera Utara.
- [17.] Nasution, D. A. D., Ramadhan, P. R., & Barus, M. D. B. *Audit Sektor Publik: Mahir dalam Pemeriksaan Pengelolaan dan Tanggung Jawab Keuangan Negara*. Uwais Inspirasi Indonesia.

- [18.] Nasution, D. A. D., & Ramadhan, P. R. (2019). Pengaruh Implementasi E-Budgeting Terhadap Transparansi Keuangan Daerah Di Indonesia. *E-Jurnal Akuntansi*, 669-693.
- [19.] Nasution, D. A. D., & Barus, M. D. B. *Monograf: Analisis Faktor-Faktor yang Mempengaruhi Kualitas Laporan Keuangan Pada Pemerintah Kota Tanjung Balai Dengan Komitmen Organisasi Sebagai Variabel Moderating*. Uwais Inspirasi Indonesia.
- [20.] Nasution, D. A. D., Nasution, A. P., & Alpi, M. F. (2019, August). Pengaruh Penerapan Smart ASN Terhadap Pengelolaan Keuangan Negara di Era Disrupsi Teknologi Indonesia 4.0. In *Seminar Nasional Sains dan Teknologi Informasi (SENSASI)* (Vol. 2, No. 1).
- [21.] Noordiawan, Dedi. 2009. *Government Accounting*, Salemba Four.
- [22.] Regulation of the Minister of Religion No. 17 of 2006 on The division formation Accounting Unit Finance and Accounting Unit of State in the Environment Ministry of Religious Affairs, Ministry of Religious Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia, 2006.